

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE REGION

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Abstract. This study examines the theoretical foundations and key development directions of social entrepreneurship within a modern social-oriented market economy. The research analyzes models such as public-private partnerships, hybrid and inclusive business models, social franchising, corporate social responsibility, and digital social services. The findings highlight the role of social entrepreneurship in creating social value, improving quality of life, and strengthening human capital. The study also identifies the importance of coordinated interaction among the state, business, civil society, and technology in ensuring sustainable development.

Key words: social entrepreneurship, public-private partnership, inclusive business, social franchising, corporate social responsibility, digital services, social innovation, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ijtimoiy tadbirkorlikning nazariy asoslari hamda zamonaviy ijtimoiy yo'naltirilgan bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitidagi asosiy rivojlanish yo'nalishlari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda davlat-xususiy sheriklik, gibrid va inklyuziv biznes modellari, ijtimoiy franshizing, korporativ ijtimoiy mas'uliyat va raqamli ijtimoiy xizmatlar ko'rib chiqilgan. Natijalar ijtimoiy tadbirkorlikning ijtimoiy qiymat yaratish, hayot sifatini oshirish va inson kapitalini rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyatini ko'rsatadi. Shuningdek, barqaror rivojlanish uchun davlat, biznes, fuqarolik jamiyati va texnologiyalar o'rtasidagi hamkorlik muhimligi asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy tadbirkorlik, davlat-xususiy sheriklik, inklyuziv biznes, ijtimoiy franshizing, korporativ ijtimoiy mas'uliyat, raqamli xizmatlar, ijtimoiy innovatsiya, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические основы и основные направления развития социального предпринимательства в условиях современной социально ориентированной рыночной экономики. В исследовании анализируются такие модели, как государственно-частное партнёрство, гибридные и инклюзивные бизнес-модели, социальный франчайзинг, корпоративная социальная ответственность и цифровые социальные услуги. Результаты показывают роль социального предпринимательства в создании социальной ценности, повышении качества жизни и развитии человеческого капитала. Также подчёркивается важность взаимодействия государства, бизнеса, гражданского общества и технологий для обеспечения устойчивого развития.

Ключевые слова: социальное предпринимательство, государственно-частное партнёрство, инклюзивный бизнес, социальный франчайзинг, корпоративная социальная ответственность, цифровые услуги, социальные инновации, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout the history of humanity's socio-economic development, it can be observed that progress has often emerged from differing interests, with economic processes largely based on norms of material self-interest. At the same time, there are spheres in which social value holds a priority alongside economic value. Taking into account that income inequality is a natural characteristic of economic systems, the entrepreneurial activities of economic entities can be directed toward economic spheres that support social goals, thereby contributing to social stability and improving quality of life.

In modern economies, such a transformation — aimed at identifying innovative solutions to social challenges and based on the provision of social services — is known as innovative social business or social entrepreneurship. When examining the economic development strategies of developed countries, it becomes clear that the primary driving force of these strategies is the human factor. Social entrepreneurship — in which commercial profit is reinvested to generate social value, support vulnerable groups, and enhance human capital productivity — has been given special importance in socio-economic development programs.

The adoption of Presidential Decree No. PF-60, dated January 28, 2022, on the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 marked an important stage in strengthening human rights, enhancing social protection, and reducing poverty as key priorities of state policy. In particular, the fourth direction of the Strategy — “Pursuing a fair social policy and developing human capital” — identified several priority tasks: expanding access to quality education and healthcare, providing social support, promoting entrepreneurship, ensuring gender equality, and improving youth policy [1].

These measures create favorable conditions for the formation and development of social entrepreneurship mechanisms — one of the key instruments supporting the country’s social development programs. The concept of social entrepreneurship has been interpreted in various ways in the literature. Since it shares many characteristics with traditional business and entrepreneurial activity, there is no single unified definition; instead, different aspects have been emphasized in different scholarly works [2].

According to Nobel Laureate Muhammad Yunus, who was among the first to introduce microfinance practices in the field of social entrepreneurship, social entrepreneurship is an innovative sphere that identifies real societal needs and provides clear directions for addressing social challenges — it represents the transformation of entrepreneurship into the social sphere [3]. Bill Drayton, founder of the Ashoka Association, described it as follows: social entrepreneurship is not about giving people fish, but teaching them to fish — and social entrepreneurs are not satisfied until they have transformed the entire system [4].

All major definitions emphasize that social entrepreneurship directly contributes to improving human well-being, fostering a prosperous society, and developing human capital. Synthesizing these interpretations, social entrepreneurship may be defined as follows:

Social entrepreneurship is a modern form of entrepreneurship oriented toward the social sphere, which involves economic activity aimed at producing social goods, creating social value, and addressing socio-economic challenges through innovative approaches, thereby contributing to economic growth and improving the well-being of various social groups.

Today, as many countries of the world continue to address the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic and evolving economic conditions, the importance of social entrepreneurship — as a form of entrepreneurship grounded in social values — has become even more evident. Gregory Dees characterized social entrepreneurs as a unique type of leader [5], while David Bornstein emphasized that if entrepreneurship serves economic development, social entrepreneurship contributes to positive change in society [6]. From these definitions, it is clear that the socio-economic significance of social entrepreneurship is reflected in its scale, the goals of economic entities, and its clearly defined development directions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of social entrepreneurship has evolved considerably since it gained academic recognition in the 1990s. Early contributions drew heavily from the broader entrepreneurship literature, adapting Schumpeter’s (1934) notion of creative destruction to a social context—where the entrepreneur is viewed not merely as a profit-seeker, but as an agent of systemic change. Schumpeter’s argument that entrepreneurial innovation disrupts existing equilibria and generates new value has been foundational in distinguishing social entrepreneurship from conventional charitable activity, positioning it instead as a dynamic, market-engaged practice oriented toward social value creation (Schumpeter, 1934; Dees, 1998).

Dees (1998) offered one of the first rigorous academic definitions, characterising social entrepreneurs as “change agents for the social sector” who adopt a mission to create and sustain social value, recognise and continuously pursue new opportunities to serve that mission, engage in a process of ongoing innovation, act boldly without being constrained by currently available resources, and demonstrate a high level of accountability to their stakeholders [5]. This definition is significant because it integrates established entrepreneurship theory—particularly the opportunity-recognition paradigm associated with Kirzner (1973)—into the social domain, thereby reinforcing social entrepreneurship as a distinct field of scholarly inquiry.

Bornstein (2004) extended this perspective by situating social entrepreneurs within a broader ecosystem

of social change, noting that “if entrepreneurship serves the economy, social entrepreneurship contributes to positive change in society” [6]. His comparative study of social entrepreneurs across six continents demonstrated that the field is not geographically limited; rather, it represents a global phenomenon shaped by local institutional conditions. Bornstein’s work highlighted the importance of the enabling environment—such as cultural norms, legal frameworks, and access to capital—as key factors influencing the effectiveness and sustainability of social enterprises.

A notable discussion in the literature concerns what Austin, Stevenson, and Wei-Skillern (2006) describe as the “narrow” and “broad” perspectives of social entrepreneurship. The narrow perspective limits the concept to non-profit organisations that apply market mechanisms to achieve social missions. In contrast, the broad perspective includes any entrepreneurial activity—whether in the non-profit, for-profit, or public sector—that prioritises the creation of social value. This distinction has important analytical implications: while the narrow perspective offers conceptual clarity, the broader perspective allows for the inclusion of hybrid models and corporate social initiatives that can generate significant social impact (Mair & Martí, 2006).

Yunus (2007) introduced a distinctive approach through the concept of “social business,” which he defined as a non-dividend, non-loss company established to address social objectives. Unlike traditional non-profit organisations, social businesses are designed to be financially self-sustaining; at the same time, unlike conventional businesses, they do not distribute profits to shareholders. Yunus’s model, illustrated by initiatives such as the Grameen Bank and its joint ventures—including the Grameen–Veolia Water Project [10]—has played an important role in advancing discussions on microfinance and entrepreneurship at the base of the pyramid [3]. At the same time, some scholars suggest that this framework may be relatively structured in scope, as it may not fully capture hybrid models that combine partial profit distribution with strong social missions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research employed a combination of analytical and comparative methods to examine the theoretical foundations of social entrepreneurship and its development directions within the region. The study is based on normative-legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, international academic literature, and empirical case studies of social enterprises operating in various countries.

A systematic literature review was conducted across scholarly sources in Uzbek, Russian, and English, covering both conceptual definitions and applied models of social entrepreneurship. The analysis of existing business models — including public-private partnerships, hybrid and inclusive business models, social franchising, corporate social responsibility, and digital social services — was carried out through desk research and comparative case analysis.

The methodological framework for identifying key development directions of social entrepreneurship in the region is grounded in a four-level interaction model. This model examines the roles and interconnections of: (1) the state, (2) civil society, (3) business, and (4) technology and innovation, as well as the reciprocal transformations that emerge across these sectors in the process of social entrepreneurship development.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of the scientific and theoretical foundations of social entrepreneurship indicates that this sector contributes to societal development at multiple levels by providing social services aimed at addressing challenges that affect overall well-being. Social services represent a category of services designed for the benefit of all members of society and differ from those offered by other economic entities in their primary orientation toward social value creation. From an economic perspective, the social sphere—encompassing services that support and enhance the quality of life of citizens—requires active and well-coordinated engagement from state institutions.

One of the key aspects of social entrepreneurship is its capacity to increase the social value added of innovations, thereby contributing to improvements in quality of life. This is reflected through several important outcomes: ensuring a minimum standard of living, developing innovative solutions to social challenges, and generating synergistic effects among resources and beneficiaries of social services [7].

In identifying the main directions for the development of social entrepreneurship, four levels of interaction were considered: the state, civil society, the business sector, and the role of innovation and technology in shaping social entrepreneurship. In addition, the analysis takes into account the transformations that occur within these sectors as a result of the development of social entrepreneurship (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Main Directions for Developing Social Entrepreneurship¹

Public-Private Partnership (PPP). Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Public-Private Partnership,” adopted on April 26, 2019, defines public-private partnership (PPP) as a legally formalized collaboration for a specified period, in which a public partner and a private partner combine their resources to implement a PPP project [8].

Article 4 of the same Law outlines the following core principles of PPP:

- Equality of the public and private partners before the law;
- Transparency in rules and procedures governing PPP implementation;
- Competition and impartiality in the selection of a private partner;
- Non-discrimination;
- Anti-corruption.

Early theoretical foundations of PPP can be associated with the work of American economist Leibenstein (1966), who introduced the concept of “X-efficiency.” He identified key “X-factors”—such as labor-management relations, organizational structures, and motivation—and applied them to analyze productivity differences between public and private enterprises, as well as the effectiveness of their operational practices.

International experience demonstrates that PPP represents an effective form of cooperation between the public and private sectors. This model has been successfully implemented in countries such as Austria, Australia, Belgium, the United Kingdom, Germany, Greece, Denmark, Italy, Israel, Ireland, Spain, Canada, Portugal, the United States, Finland, France, South Korea, and Japan. In the social sector, PPP is particularly well developed in countries with high living standards and strong social protection systems, including the United Kingdom, the United States, Spain, France, and Japan [9].

Notable examples also include Chile’s effective use of PPP in pension system reforms, as well as the experiences of South Africa and Colombia in applying PPP models within the education sector. In the context of social entrepreneurship, where innovative and sustainable business models are required to address social challenges, PPP offers a structured framework that combines public resources with private sector capabilities. Its key advantages for social entrepreneurship include:

1. Resource mobilization: PPP enables access to financial, human, and technological resources from both sectors;
2. Risk sharing: Financial, organizational, and market risks are distributed between public and private partners;
3. Enhanced innovation: Joint research and development activities foster innovative approaches to social project implementation;
4. Expanded impact: PPP strengthens the scalability of social entrepreneurship initiatives across regions.

Examples of successful PPP initiatives include the Grameen–Veolia Water Project (2008), which provided access to clean drinking water in rural areas of Bangladesh [10], and the Better Buildings Partnership [11], which brought together local governments and private property owners to improve energy efficiency and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in commercial buildings, thereby supporting environmental sustainability.

¹ Author’s own framework based on researches

Hybrid and Inclusive Business Models. A hybrid business model refers to a form of social enterprise that combines elements of both non-profit and for-profit organizations. It may adopt various legal and organizational forms, such as corporations, low-profit limited liability companies (L3C), or social-purpose corporations. Although their financial structures and operational mechanisms may differ, these organizations are unified by a common social mission.

This model is typically categorized into three types based on the relationship between commercial and non-profit activities and the source of value creation [12]:

1. **Embedded model:** A single organization integrates its social mission into its core operations, using generated profits to sustain its social activities. An example is TOMS Shoes, which donates a pair of shoes to a child in need for every pair sold.

2. **Integrated model:** Organizations with different value propositions, customer segments, and value chains collaborate through a shared social mission and strategic partnerships. For example, Kiva connects lenders with low-income entrepreneurs through an online platform.

3. **Parallel model:** Two organizations operate separately but share governance structures, such as a common board of directors. Commercial entities contribute part of their profits to support non-profit activities. Newman's Own, which allocates a significant share of its profits to charitable causes, exemplifies this model.

An inclusive business model, in contrast, is a sustainable approach that creates value for low-income population groups by integrating them into the value chain as customers, producers, entrepreneurs, or employees. This model not only expands economic opportunities but also supports employment generation [13].

The inclusive business model is based on the following key principles:

- **Human development impact:** It contributes to increasing incomes, meeting basic needs, and supporting vulnerable groups such as persons with disabilities, women, and youth;
- **Self-sustainability:** Although initial financial support may be required, the model is designed to achieve long-term financial independence;
- **Environmental sustainability:** It minimizes environmental impact and contributes to addressing ecological challenges, including reducing emissions, managing waste, and preserving biodiversity.

The advantages of this model for both businesses and society—particularly for low-income groups—are diverse and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Beneficial Aspects of the Inclusive Business Model for Business and Society²

Advantages for Business	Advantages for Low-Income Population
Generates and multiplies profit; Develops new market segments; Increases innovation activity; Expands the pool of labor resources; Strengthens the value chain.	Incomes rise through the creation of new jobs; Primary needs are met; Productivity increases; Builds confidence in the future among the poor.

Social Franchising

Social franchising is a form of franchising aimed at addressing social challenges rather than prioritizing commercial objectives [14]. This approach is based on applying the principles of commercial franchising with the goal of expanding social impact rather than maximizing private profit. Social franchising generally operates in two main forms.

In the first form, contractual relationships are established in which an independent coordinating organization provides individual operators with the opportunity to join a franchising network. The agreement includes a defined set of services in a particular field, developed according to a structured plan prepared by the franchisor. Upon joining the network, participants gain access to a range of support services, including professional training, brand usage and promotion, subsidized or patented materials and equipment, mentoring, and expert консультации.

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inclusive_business_model

The second form of social franchising focuses primarily on creating employment opportunities for low-income populations and addressing social challenges through collaborative arrangements and partnership agreements. A prominent example is the De Kringwinkel network in Flanders, which employs approximately 5,000 people. In developing countries, social franchising has been successfully applied in areas such as emergency healthcare, pharmaceutical distribution, HIV/AIDS testing and counseling, and reproductive health services.

In addition, networking and outreach approaches are used to strengthen social franchising systems. For example, social entrepreneurs are often invited to participate in events organized by large companies, where they can present their projects and build partnerships. This practice is widely applied in developed countries and contributes to scaling social initiatives.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a self-regulating business model that encourages companies to operate responsibly toward themselves, their stakeholders, and society as a whole. Within this framework, companies proactively assess and manage the economic, social, and environmental impacts of their activities.

Several main types of CSR can be distinguished:

1. Environmental responsibility: Companies aim to minimize the environmental impact of their operations by reducing waste, promoting recycling, increasing green coverage, and developing environmentally friendly products and services.
2. Ethical responsibility: This includes ensuring fair and equal treatment of employees regardless of age, gender, or background, as well as delivering high-quality products and services to customers.
3. Philanthropic responsibility: Companies allocate a portion of their profits to charitable initiatives and actively support social development projects.
4. Financial responsibility: To maintain financial sustainability, preserve employment, and support environmental and social initiatives, companies continuously adopt modern technologies and improve operational efficiency [15].

Examples of companies implementing CSR practices include Starbucks and General Motors. Starbucks supports its employees through stock options and additional benefits in healthcare, education, and family support, and has committed to reducing greenhouse gas emissions and waste by 50% by 2030 [16]. General Motors has provided \$60 million in grants to more than 400 non-profit organizations in the United States addressing social issues and has committed to using 100% renewable electricity at its U.S. facilities by 2025 [17].

Digital Social Services (Tech for Good)

“Tech for Good” refers to the application of digital technologies to deliver services aimed at addressing social challenges. These services span a wide range of sectors, including healthcare, education, finance, and advisory services. In Uzbekistan, important steps have been taken in this direction, including the adoption of Presidential Resolution No. PQ-162 (May 24, 2023), which focuses on improving the accessibility and quality of digital services and accelerating digital transformation across sectors.

Examples of digital social services in Uzbekistan include platforms such as www.gov.uz, www.president.uz, the official website of the “Inson” Social Services Agency (www.ihma.uz), educational platforms such as Khan Academy (uz.khanacademy.org), and mobile applications like Click Up, which integrates digital tools for charitable services.

The key advantages of digital social services include their ability to deliver efficient services to large segments of the population within a short time frame, while reducing costs, including time-related expenses. At the same time, several important challenges remain:

- Infrastructure limitations in certain regions, including low internet speed and limited digital literacy;
- Data privacy and cybersecurity concerns;
- Technical implementation and maintenance costs;
- Inclusivity challenges, including ensuring access for low-income groups and providing multilingual service delivery.

Integrated Analysis of Social Entrepreneurship Development

The analysis of the scientific and theoretical foundations of social entrepreneurship confirms that this sector occupies a unique position at the intersection of business activity, civil society, and public policy. The

development directions examined—public-private partnerships, hybrid and inclusive business models, social franchising, CSR, and digital social services—are interconnected and mutually reinforcing within the context of a modern social-oriented market economy.

Public-private partnerships have demonstrated strong potential as a mechanism for mobilizing resources and distributing risks in addressing complex social challenges. Examples such as the Grameen–Veolia project in Bangladesh and the Better Buildings Partnership illustrate how PPP models can simultaneously generate economic value and produce meaningful social outcomes. In Uzbekistan, the Law on Public-Private Partnership (2019) provides a solid legal foundation, while further strengthening institutional capacity and expanding awareness among private sector participants will enhance its effectiveness.

Hybrid and inclusive business models demonstrate that social entrepreneurship can successfully balance financial sustainability with social objectives. The embedded, integrated, and parallel models offer flexible approaches depending on organizational capacity, stakeholder structure, and target beneficiaries. In particular, inclusive business models provide a sustainable pathway for reducing poverty and inequality while supporting economic participation at the base of the pyramid.

Social franchising represents a promising direction with significant development potential in the region. While its applications in healthcare and employment generation are well established internationally, further adaptation to local institutional and cultural contexts can expand its effectiveness in Uzbekistan.

Corporate Social Responsibility is becoming increasingly relevant not only for large corporations but also for medium-sized enterprises, particularly as Uzbekistan continues to integrate into global markets. International examples demonstrate how structured CSR strategies can support measurable social and environmental outcomes.

Overall, the development of social entrepreneurship in the region—as illustrated in Figure 2—requires coordinated interaction across four key domains: state regulation and support, civil society participation, private sector engagement, and technological innovation. The synergy among these components enables more effective and sustainable outcomes than isolated efforts (Figure 2).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Social entrepreneurship directions that are closely interconnected and complementary in their social service characteristics are advancing to a new qualitative stage in the current phase of development of a social-

oriented market economy. The analytical and evaluative indicators of social services, social entrepreneurship, and service systems are increasingly being shaped in accordance with modern socio-economic principles, while effectively utilizing the opportunities provided by public-private partnerships. This approach facilitates the active involvement of investors and economic entities in production processes, financial support, technological development, and management practices.

Future research may focus on assessing the social impact of these models within specific regional contexts, developing sustainable financing mechanisms that reduce reliance on public funding, and strengthening an enabling ecosystem for social entrepreneurs in Uzbekistan.

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